

Expression of Cadherin-11(CDH-11) Immunohistochemical marker in Gastric Cancer and its Correlation with the Clinicopathological Parameters – A Pilot Study

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Citation: Divya Dhanabal, Vasugi Arumugam, Arthi M, Meryl Saji, Sandhya Sundaram. Expression of Cadherin-11(CDH-11) Immunohistochemical marker in Gastric Cancer and its correlation with the clinicopathological parameters – A Pilot Study. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(9):1-10.

Received Date: 12 September, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 18 September, 2024; **Published Date:** 20 September, 2024

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ABSTRACT

Gastric carcinoma is the fifth most common cancer worldwide and the leading cause of cancer-related mortality. Predictive biomarkers of the clinical outcome remain elusive. Cadherin -11 (CDH-11) plays key role in the movement of neural crest cells and is involved in bone maintenance and metabolism and also in tumour immune escape. Dysregulation of CDH-11 contributes to many pathologic processes, such as inflammation, fibrosis, cellular migration, invasion, epithelial-mesenchymal transition, and carcinogenesis. Thus, it could be thought as a potential prognostic biomarker and therapeutic target. The study aimed to assess CDH-11 expression in gastric cancer and correlate the findings with the clinicopathological parameters. IHC staining was done on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tumour sections of 27 patients with gastric cancer. Pylorus was the most common tumour site observed. 66% of the cases were intestinal-type adenocarcinoma and 34% were poorly differentiated adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell morphology. Lymphovascular and Perineural invasion was noted in 13 and 12 cases respectively. None of the cases had distant metastasis. Twelve cases (44%) showed strong nuclear positivity for CDH-11. 5 cases (18%) showed cytoplasmic expression. Ten cases (37%) were negative for CDH-11 expression. The statistical analysis of this pilot study throws insight into the expression of CDH11 and its association with various clinical parameters. CDH-11 expression was positive in the poorly differentiated

[Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour \(ICMCRJ\) 2024 | Volume 3 | Issue 9](#)

tumors especially in tumours with lymphovascular invasion. This finding indicates the possible role of CDH11 as a predictive marker. However, further studies with a larger sample size are warranted to elaborate on the clinical implication of expressions of CDH11 thoroughly.

Keywords: CDH11; Gastric Carcinoma; Immunohistochemistry; Biomarker; Lymphovascular Invasion

INTRODUCTION

Gastric cancer ranks fifth in global cancer and is the third most significant contributor to cancer-related mortality^[1]. Among early-stage gastric cancer, the five-year survival rate is 83-99.5%, whereas for advanced-stage gastric cancer, it is 14-55%^[2]. Gastric cancer is characterised by inflammation, fibrosis and EMT [Epithelial mesenchymal transition], which plays a vital role in epithelial malignancy and metastases^[3].

The EMT process disrupts cell-cell adhesion and cellular polarity, remodelling of the cytoskeleton, and cell-matrix adhesion. It is highly associated with migratory properties. In cancers, EMT inducers are hypoxia, cytokines, and growth factors secreted by the tumour microenvironment, stroma crosstalk, metabolic changes and immune responses.^[4]

CDH-11 was discovered in mouse osteoblasts and is a type II classical cadherin from the family of integral membrane proteins that help in calcium-dependent cell-cell adhesion. It is located on human chromosome 16q22.1.6. Dysregulation of CDH11 contributes to many pathologic processes like inflammation, fibrosis, cellular migration, invasion, EMT, and carcinogenesis^[5]. EMT is triggered by inflammation, and the response in the process of chronic inflammation becomes cancerous. EMT is becoming a primary target of interest in cancer therapy treatment^[6,7]. Hence, more knowledge about the role of EMT in metastasis and its control is essential. The role of CDH11 in GC progression remains unclear. CDH-11 expression, if proven, can be an excellent predictive tool for metastases and can be used in treating patients with gastric cancer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As a pilot retrospective study, the sample size was at a minimum threshold of 27 cases. Inclusion criteria: Cases with histopathologic diagnosis of Gastric Carcinoma were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Cases with histopathologic diagnosis of Benign tumour and all other neoplasms were excluded.

The Patient details were collected from the Internal hospital database and the Medical Records Department of SRIHER, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India, based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

In this study, CDH-11 Immunohistochemical stain was done on formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded tumour sections of 27 patients with gastric cancer. The patient's demographic details and clinicopathological parameters were obtained from the medical records section. The anti-CDH11 antibody used in this study is a polyclonal IgG human, mouse-reactive antibody. The dilution used here was 1:100. Anti-CDH11 antibody in 2% BSA/PBS was added overnight at four °C. After this, it was incubated with a secondary antibody for 30 minutes at room temperature.

Positive control: Human Placenta.

Strong CDH-11 expression on the cell membrane was considered to be positive.

Two independent Pathologists saw each case slide. In the present study, positive CDH11 staining was defined as the positivity of CDH11 expression observed on the cellular membrane of cancer cells by IHC.

RESULTS

A total of 27 cases were included in the study, of which 20 were males and 7 were females (**Figure-2**). There was a male predominance in our study. The mean age of presentation was 57 years, with the minimum age of presentation being 29 years and the maximum age of 77 years (**Figure-1**). Pylorus is the most common tumour site (**Figure-3**). Most cases (66%) were intestinal-type adenocarcinoma (**Figure-4**). Rest was poorly differentiated adenocarcinoma with signet ring cell morphology. Lymphovascular invasion was noted in 13 cases. Perineural invasion was noted in 12 cases. None of the cases had distant metastasis. Twelve cases (44%) showed strong nuclear positivity for CDH-11 (**Figure-5**). 5 cases (18%) showed cytoplasmic expression (**Figure-5**). 10 cases (37%) were negative for CDH-11 expression (**Figure-5**). Correlation of CDH, 11 expressions with age (**Table-II**), gender (**Table-III**), tumour site (**Table-IV**), histological type (**Table-V**), histological grade (**Table-VI**), Lymphovascular (LV) invasion (**Figure-7**) (**Table-VII**), Perineural (PN) invasion (**Figure-7**) (**Table-VIII**), regional lymph node status (**Table-IX**), were tabulated.

Table I: Demographic and clinicopathological data of the study samples

Parameter	n (%)
Age	
>50yrs	19 (70%)
<50yrs	8 (30%)
Tumor Site	
Pylorus	7 (26%)
Body	7 (26%)
Distal stomach	1 (4%)
Curvature	3 (11%)
Cardia	2 (7%)
Antrum	7 (26%)
Histologic Grade	
Poorly differentiated	13 (48%)
Moderately differentiated	13 (48%)
Well differentiated	1 (4%)
Lymphovascular Invasion	
Present	15 (56%)
Absent	12 (44%)
Perineural Invasion	
Present	9 (33%)
Absent	18 (67%)
CDH11 Expression	
Positive [Membrane positive]	14 (52%)
Negative	13 (48%)

Table-II: Histologic Type vs CDH11 Expression

HISTOLOGIC TYPE	Positive [Membrane positive]	Cytoplasmic Positive
Adenocarcinoma - Intestinal type	5	4

Adenocarcinoma with focal signet ring cells	1	0
Adenocarcinoma with focal signet ring cells .	2	0
Signet ring cell carcinoma	1	0

Cross-tab analysis: CDH-11 positivity is more commonly observed in the adenocarcinoma-intestinal type, which is also the predominant histologic type in this study.

Table-III: Histologic Grade vs CDH11 Expression

HISTOLOGIC GRADE	Positive [Membrane positive]	Cytoplasmic Positive
Moderately differentiated	2	2
Poorly differentiated	7	2

Cross-tab analysis: CDH-11 positivity is more frequently observed in Poorly differentiated carcinomas.

Table-IV: Lymphovascular Invasion vs CDH11 Expression

LV INVASION	Positive [Membrane positive]	Cytoplasmic Positive
Absent	3	3
Present	6	1

Cross-tab analysis: CDH-11 positivity is seen more often in carcinomas with lymphovascular invasion.

Table-V: Perineural Invasion vs CDH11 Expression

PN INVASION	Positive [Membrane positive]	Cytoplasmic Positive
Absent	4	3
Present	5	1

CROSS TAB ANALYSIS- CDH-11 positivity is slightly more often in carcinomas with perineural invasion.

Figure 1:

- A - CDH-11 showing strong Membrane expression in tumour cells (IHC 20x).
- B - CDH-11 showing membrane expression in tumour cells (IHC 20x).
- C - CDH-11 showing negative expression in tumour cells (IHC 20x).

DISCUSSION

Gastric cancer is the fifth most common cancer worldwide, according to GLOBOCON 2022^[8]. The statistical analysis of this pilot study throws good insight into the expression of CDH11 and its association with various clinical parameters taken in the patients. Descriptive statistics reveals the full description of the dataset's characteristics but is limited to the variation in statistical analysis data. Therefore, this discussion will focus on interpreting the findings, the clinical parameters, and the concurrent findings in the literature. CDH11, a member of the super family of cadherins involved in calcium-dependent cell-cell adhesion, is reported to play an essential role in the metastasis of various cancers Pishvaian et al., 2017^[9]; Yokoyama et al., 2020^[10].

In this Pilot study, the mean age for patients was 57.7 years, with a standard deviation of 14.3, ranging from 29 to 77 years. It is representative of the general gastric cancer epidemiology because most of the patients are diagnosed as older people; the age of diagnosis is 65 and 73 years Arnold et al., 2015^[11]. Description of the sex

distribution shows that more men suffered from this condition compared to women, with a ratio of 20:7, which is to the world pattern since men are more likely to contract this disease Ferlay et al., 2019 ^[12]. This difference might be due to the genetic, hormonal, and lifestyle factors in men that would make them prone to the disease and that they are more likely to smoke and drink in more significant amounts Crew & Neugut, 2006 ^[13]. Awareness of these demographic characteristics allows identifying people at high risk and, therefore, the devolution of screening and preventive strategies.

The most common site of the tumour in this study was the pylorus, with 7 cases. This result also agrees with other studies and describes a higher frequency of involvement of the pylorus by gastric cancer, which might be explained by the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the pyloric region of the stomach Crew & Neugut, 2006 ^[13]. The histologic examination concluded the most common type was adenocarcinoma of the intestinal type, with 18 cases. Lauren's classification long established that the most common type of gastric cancer is represented by the histological intestinal-type adenocarcinoma, especially in the case of being associated with older patients Lauren, 1965 ^[14]. In most of the tumours in this study, 13 cases were poorly differentiated, associated with a more aggressive clinical course and poorer prognosis Lauren, 1965; Bosman et al., 2010^[15]. Poorly differentiated tumours do not respond well to treatment and are relatively more likely to develop early metastasis.

Lymphovascular and peripheral invasion were present in almost half of the cases: 13 had Lymphovascular invasion, and 12 had Perineural invasion. Lymphovascular and perineural invasion are strong predictors and are widely documented in many studies for aggressive tumour behaviour. Both are associated with poor prognosis and high rates of recurrence Wang et al., 2018 ^[16]; Deng et al., 2019 ^[17]. Besides, the presence of LV, in a way, brings about a door opening for further migration of the tumour cells through the lymphatic and vascular systems, thus adding the regional lymph nodes and distant organs into the gamut of metastasis ^[18]. On the other hand, PN invasion means that the tumour cells have invaded the perineural spaces, further evoking a severe pain state and functional impairment. This is another reason a detailed histopathological examination is necessary to document these invasion parameters, vital to accurate staging and subsequent prognostication.

The expression of CDH11 was positive in 12, negative in 10, and cytoplasmic positivity was seen in 5 cases. In our Pilot study, CDH-11 expression is positive in 7 poorly differentiated cases (58%) out of 12 positive cases. This is a significant finding as poorly differentiated patients have a poor prognosis, and the tumour behaviour is

aggressive compared to well and moderately-differentiated patients. In the same way, six cases (50%) of lymphovascular invasion showed positivity. The tumours with lymphovascular invasion have a high recurrence rate and poor prognosis.

CDH-11 positivity is more common among patients aged 50 and above and in men. Tumors located in the antrum frequently exhibit CDH-11 expression. Furthermore, it is also prevalent in adenocarcinomas, intestinal types, and poorly differentiated carcinomas. CDH-11 positivity is commonly associated with carcinomas showing lymphovascular invasion and is slightly more prevalent in those with perineural invasion. Moreover, CDH-11 positivity is often observed in carcinomas with lymphovascular metastases.

The major limitation of this study is that distant metastasis data yielded a lack of variation, which rendered it impossible to carry out more statistically complex analyses such as logistic regression and Fisher's exact test. Small sample sizes in studies may reduce statistical power. Finally, given that the study is retrospective, there is a high likelihood of selection bias, mainly because the participants in the study are drawn from only those who had data available. Given that results from this Pilot study have to be validated and studied further with larger prospective cohorts and with the availability of follow-up data in future studies, to evaluate the possible predictive value of CDH11 expression in more detail.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the present study unravels descriptive analysis of CDH11 expression and its association with clinical parameters in gastric cancer patients. These results will significantly advance current knowledge regarding CDH11 in gastric cancer and pinpoint the importance of demographic and clinical features in the progression of a disease. The CDH-11 expression was positive in the more aggressive group of tumours, which were poorly differentiated and seen in tumours with lymphovascular invasion. This finding indicates the possible role of CDH11 as an essential predictive marker. However, further studies with a larger sample size and advanced statistical analyses should be necessary to elaborate on the clinical implication of expressions of CDH11 thoroughly. These future studies should also proceed with elucidating the molecular mechanisms behind the CDH11-mediated tumour progression to devise targeted therapies that will improve the well-being of the patients.

The Institutional Ethics Committee, SRIHER, approved this Pilot study.

REF: IEC-NI/24/JUL/96/115.

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